

Happiness as a self state and trait of consciousness: clinical hypnosis and saliva molecular biomarkers - a brief revision

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Abstract

The relationship between consciousness and neural activity, i.e., between mental and brain states, has been widely studied. However, the relation between consciousness and its biochemical markers is still undetermined. Altered states of consciousness (ASC), can be a learning process for the achievement of subjective states of happiness. Clinical hypnosis and guided meditation are fast learning techniques, leading to the desired subjective state. This subjective state of happiness has saliva molecular biomarkers and can be correlated with psychological assessments. Therefore, it is proposed a new approach of altered state of consciousness induction, associated with subjective states of happiness, using a specific methodology and analysis, named The Pursuit of Happiness model. This model: (1) Studies the use of a hypnotic induction technique, named The Way of Happiness, to achieve states and traits of consciousness associated happiness. (2) Proposes, in parallel, a biomedical analysis named: States and Traits of Consciousness: Saliva Molecular Biomarkers. (3) Correlates the objective saliva molecular biomarkers with the subjective psychological assessments. (4) Develops a Knowledge Discovery Database with data-mining algorithms and bioinformatics tools to discover patterns that relates ASC, subjective states of happiness, saliva molecular biomarkers, peak experiences and self-consciousness.

Keywords

Consciousness, happiness, neuroproteomics, data mining, bioinformatics

INTRODUCTION

Consciousness can be defined as the immediate perception that the subject has of what is happening inside or outside of him, including the knowledge of his thoughts, feelings and actions. Consciousness is understood as the momentary reality that the individual experiences according to his perception and self-consciousness [1,2] and correlates with the concept of experience described in Nietzsche's philosophy, with triple meaning of immediacy, significance and incommensurability [3].

The concept of ASC, defined as 'a qualitative alteration in the overall pattern of mental functioning, such that the experimenter feels his consciousness is radically different from the way it functions ordinarily' [4], may be understood as common ground among neuroscience, medicine and the science of consciousness.

ASC have been used in medicine as an alternative mechanism for the acquisition and integration of knowledge [5]. Both natural and induced have been described as ways to reach an altered state of consciousness.

The natural one corresponds to meditative practices, in which the learning process for the achievement of that ASC is usually long.

The induction techniques are faster, as they always involve a second individual, in addition to the subject of the practice. That individual leads the induction and facilitates the achievement of a desired ASC.

Meditative practices have been linked to the induction of ASC and to neuroplasticity, possibly leading to new brain correlates [6]. In fact, they induce long-term changes in self-consciousness, observed both in high and low level cortical representations [7].

The neurophysiological changes induced by meditative practices are of two types: (1) occurring during meditative practices - state changes, and (2) accumulating over months or years and persisting even when not on meditative practices - i.e., trait changes [8]. Therefore, also ASC can be seen as state and trait of consciousness.

One way of attaining the proposed state and trait of consciousness, is the mindfulness meditative practice. Mindfulness is described as sustainable awareness aimed at a non-reactive consciousness [8, 9, 10]. This promotes physical and mental well-being with positive emotional traits [11], and modulates the limbic-neocortical emotional systems connectivity [12], therefore the need to integrate their principles in medicine [13].

Meditative practices and induction techniques, e.g. clinical hypnosis, [14, 15], respectively natural and inductive technique, have been linked to the attainment of ASC, leading to neuropsychophysiological and anatomical correlates [16, 17, 18]. These are well studied, and have been recognized as an effective clinical tool [19]. These techniques are also a vehicle for inducing peak experiences, associated with subjective states of happiness [16,

20] and described as “flow state” [21]. Moreover, induction techniques, are used as first-line therapeutic practices of acute and chronic syndromes [22].

Few findings describe specific biomarkers that can be elicited through ASC, showing some relationship with psycho-neuro-immune-endocrine models [19]. Moreover, different ways of reaching, perpetuating and intensifying subjective states of happiness, through induced ASC, should be scientifically approached, because they have been rarely associated with biochemical markers.

In fact, ASC and the induction of subjective states of happiness and peak experiences have been only extensively and specifically associated to endogenous dimethyltryptamine pathway [23, 24]. At this point it is postulated that these ASC, natural or induced, may be associated to the sense of self-consciousness, and used to promote subjective states of happiness, and ultimately peak experiences.

Consciousness Evaluation

Diagnosis using neuroimaging and electrophysiological tools in search for objective markers of consciousness is being employed. However, such tools cannot be considered as diagnostic per se, but as assistants to the clinical evaluation, which, at present, remains the gold standard. As well as the Glasgow Coma Scale and Coma Recovery Scale–Revised remains the gold standard in the behavioral assessment [25].

The fMRI and EEG recordings provide mutually consistent evidence on the neural correlates of ecstatic meditations. The multiplicity of brain states suggests that there may be a vast ASC available through meditation, depending on which brain regions are given awareness and which are inhibited from awareness [16].

Also, different scales have been used to assess consciousness in its different components, (1) being evaluated as an ASC [26], (2) as an induced state and trait of consciousness [27], (3) as a study of self-consciousness [28] or (4) possibly as associated with subjective states of happiness [29]. These different scales may evaluate autobiographic memories of happiness recalled from the extended consciousness (the autobiographic self) of the subject [30].

In this study, the gold standard are the behavioral and psychological assessments, by the application of scales that evaluate the subjective and phenomenological experience, which should contribute to certify that the subjects are in the desired state and trait of consciousness.

The biomedical analysis uses saliva molecular biomarkers, stored in Biobanco-iMM, Lisbon Academic Medical Center, Lisbon, Portugal. The neuroproteomic analysis of the saliva molecular biomarkers is expected to enable the recognition of states and traits of consciousness, if sufficient data is gathered and analyzed with data-mining algorithms and bioinformatics tools. The objective here is to provide an alternative, innovative and non-invasive consciousness assessment in its different components and states, e.g. happiness.

Neuroproteomics of Consciousness and Happiness

The problem is that there is no validated objective “consciousness meter” that can be used as a proof or disproof of consciousness [31]. The real challenge lies in designing tools to allow an objective, scientific measure of subjective report [32].

Indeed, this is already an active area of study [33, 34] and could in principle produce biomarkers of consciousness that allow for reporting the phenomenological experience [35]. Therefore the need to understand thoroughly the neural correlates of consciousness, possibly through salivary molecular biomarkers.

Neurophysiologic mechanisms studied with neuroproteomic analysis of Serum S-100, serum NSE, S-100 CSF and NSE CSF [36] are correlated with the prediction of regaining consciousness after global cerebral ischemia [37], and could be seen as biomarker of self-consciousness after cardiopulmonary resuscitation. Other biomarkers obtained through proteomics like MAP-2 can in principle provide insight into the mechanism of neuronal remodeling [38] as well as discriminate between patients

with deficits in consciousness [39].

Other example, but linked to physiological mechanism, is the N,N-DMT, obtained with liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry [24]. Biochemical, physiological, and behavioral experiments indicate that N,N-DMT is an endogenous agonist for the sigma-1 receptor [40] or serotonin 5-HT_{1A/5-HT_{2A}}-R receptor [41]. These studies, could uncover the neurologic controversy of ASC and the induction of a state and trait of consciousness associated with happiness and peak experiences [23]. It is already known that optimism and positive emotional states also modify the salivary proteomic biomarker profile [42].

Moreover, using proteomics, it would be possible to monitor the modulatory effects of metabotropic muscarinic receptors, on inhibition of adenylyl cyclase, excitation of phospholipase C, and activation of K⁺ channels. In turn, such activation would alter the phosphorylation states of intracellular proteins, ion channels, enzymes, and transcription factors, from millisecond to long-term time scales [43].

However, no one yet, seems to have combined proteomic technology with changes in brain states resulting from experience, the environment or how it influences the conscious experience, e.g. happiness or self-consciousness, and therefore the main objective of such study.

In addition, peptides such as enkephalins might as well serve as additional parameters for influencing and reflecting baseline states and traits of consciousness, as measured by analytical high-pressure liquid chromatography on peptide-containing fractions of plasma for identification by matrix-assisted laser desorption–ionization–time-of-flight mass spectrometry [43].

Biomarkers that reflect mental state have been identified in saliva. These biomarkers, like amylase, chromogranin A, and cytokines, are known stress markers, but there are few reports demonstrating their relation with a positive mental state [44].

Concluding, the physiological approach through molecular biomarker analysis of saliva might be a genuine and interesting framework for the research of these study internal variables [45].

However, it would be important to bear in mind that this study would show at best an index of a degree of a state and trait and consciousness, not consciousness itself.

Experiments characterizing biological correlates might provide insight into the causal relationship between physical and phenomenological descriptions.

Data Mining and Patterns Recognition

A complete set of neuroproteomic and psychological data is collected in this work to study the (inter subjective) happiness state and trait of consciousness. The resulting amount of information embedded is hence massive.

Only relying on standard methods for analyzing this data base (e.g., assessment of the covariance between variables) might provide sub-optimal results due to the high number of measured quantities and possible non-linear relationships between them.

Data mining solutions are then planned to discover and model patterns that relate ASC, subjective states of happiness, saliva molecular biomarkers, peak experiences and self-consciousness. The development of a user-friendly software environment is also scoped to enable a throughout exploration of the information embedded in the database. Specifically, data visualization techniques shall be adopted for the interactive query of related ASC and physiological relationships. Finally, data classification and regression algorithms based on neural network models are devised for operational applications such as recognizing ASC from the analysis of salivary samples.

CONCLUSION

Summing up there are evidences of innovative and non-invasive techniques of evaluation of states and traits of consciousness, e.g. subjective happiness or self-consciousness. This evaluation combines both phenomenological and subjective data, obtained through psychological assessments and scales, and neuroproteomic and objective data, obtained through salivary sampling.

Data mining solutions are implemented to offer pattern

recognitions to correlate both evaluations: subjective and objective.

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